

ESL Learning Practice and Follow-up in Middle East Asia

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ABSTRACT:

This paper reports the results of a qualitative research study designed to examine the effects of guided written and oral reflections for developing reflective thinking skills¹ among Arab-Muslim female student teachers in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teacher education program in Israel. Guidance was provided in the framework of a one year practicum. Besides employing some qualitative research methods such as observations and conducting interviews, a pre-post questionnaire to examine changes in the participants' perceptions of reflective skills was administered. The results indicate some improvement in the students' reflective abilities. However, a more structured practice teaching program, time and ample opportunities for practice and reflection are needed to help Arab Muslim student teachers further develop their reflective abilities.

KEYWORDS: Developing reflective skills, Guided reflections, EFL, Student Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Developing reflective thinking means helping student teachers think about their experiences, analyze their beliefs, values or knowledge in relation to these experiences and consider options or alternatives for action (Ferraro, 2000). This research deals with the issue of developing reflective thinking skills among Arab Muslim female student teachers in a pre-service teacher education program in Israel. On the one hand, their previous learning experiences are based on rote learning and memorization; on the other hand, they study in a Jewish college that adopts Western pedagogy that requires students to reflect on their learning. In addition, they are trained to be qualified to teach English, which requires them to develop their reflective skills. The purpose of the study is to examine the ways, strategies and techniques employed for developing the student teachers' reflective abilities. These strategies included lesson observation and evaluation, post-lesson discussions and portfolios providing guided written and verbal reflections. Written guided reflections were required for evaluating the lessons taught by them, their classmates and the school mentors. They referred to the pros and cons of each lesson, indicating what should be included in future lessons, and mentioning the reasons. Similarly, guided reflections were part of the post-lesson discussions held during the team meetings.

Learning and teaching have become a lifelong process rather than an end in itself. It is a lifelong experience of trial, error, and inquiry (Al-Issa, 2005; Strakov'a, 2009) . Therefore, student teachers are expected to be reflective thinkers and teacher educators are their advisors (Farr,

2010). In an EFL context, which is also the context of this research, language teacher educators are seen as facilitators and are expected to provide support and opportunities for practice and reflection (Jarvis, Holford & Griffin, 2004; Jarvis, 2006; Richards & Farrel, 2005; Richards & Farrell, 2011). They are expected to help student teachers develop their reflective skills for self-evaluation, knowledge and pedagogy in general (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1999), and language pedagogy in specific (Richards & Farrell, 2011). To do so, teacher educators must hold frequent meetings with the students to analyze situations in order to help them develop their reflective skills. The research emerged from the need to help my students be more independent thinkers and reflectors in order to be well-qualified EFL teachers in the 21st century. The patterns of thinking and modes of behavior of my students are not in line with Western style pedagogy adopted in some educational environments in the Gulf States and in the context of this study. So the focus is on students constructing meaning rather than teachers serving as sources of knowledge and on creativity and reflective practice rather than on rote learning. Conducting this study was important for me as a teacher educator who comes from the same culture and is considered a role model who realized the advantages of acquiring reflective thinking skills while pursuing graduate studies in the United States of America. Moreover, I consider myself an agent for change who endeavors to work constantly and systematically to provide my students with emotional as well as professional help and support through multiple opportunities for practice teaching to develop their reflective skills. The present study was aimed at examining the effect of guided reflective techniques employed to develop reflective thinking skills among Arab pre-service female teachers in Israel, who are highly influenced by their previous learning experiences which were based on rote learning and memorization. Thus, the research question was: what effect do these guided reflective techniques have on the development of their reflective thinking skills?

THE STUDY

Developing reflective skills among student teachers Reflecting means thinking about actions with a view to their importance, evaluating them, and seeking possible solutions or alternatives (Ferraro, 2000). It involves challenging and questioning current beliefs and assumptions, and seeking alternatives (Murray & Kujundzic, 2005). According to Ma & Ren (2011) reflective teaching is the process of self-study or self learning, where the teacher learns about himself/herself through exploring teaching and learning activities (Ma & Ren, 2011). It even makes him/her more initiative and responsible. Many studies have been conducted to examine the usefulness of reflective practice in teacher education. For example, the findings of a study which was designed to examine the reflective journal entries of 42 trainee teachers during practicum in Malaysian schools indicated that approximately 77% of the trainees mentioned that the reflective journal "assisted them in evaluating their teaching methods, strengths and weaknesses of their own teaching, problems in teaching, and identifying materials and aids for their teaching" (Nooreiny, 2007, p. 205). Another study was reported by Pedro (2005) which focused on the use of reflective practice by pre-service teachers who were required to reflect on their own performance as well as their peers by completing a reflective learning journal. The findings suggest that the participants of the research "had a general understanding of reflection and learned to reflect through various opportunities, and in different contexts" (p. 49). Another research study was conducted by Clarke and Otaky (2006) to examine the appropriateness of reflective practice among female student teachers in a new teacher education program at the Higher Colleges of Technology (HCT) in the UAE. The findings reveal that Emirati women

wholeheartedly embrace reflective practice "demonstrating considerable self-awareness of their capacity to growth, development and change" (Clarke & Otkay, 2006, 118).

THE NEED FOR DEVELOPING REFLECTIVE SKILLS FOR ESL/EFL STUDENT TEACHERS

In the literature on second-language teaching, theorists have presented a contemporary perspective by recommending a variety of approaches, strategies, and techniques to teach the language effectively and help learners learn successfully (Richards & Farrell, 2011). Language Teacher Education programs (LTE) must encourage and support students for risk-taking with alternative models and experiencing them (Farr, 2010). Developing teacher expertise is an ongoing process that cannot be achieved in year-long LTE programs (Ibid.). Therefore, trainees are encouraged to discover what works best in the context where they will work, reflect on what is happening around them in class, and learn from experiences (Strakov'a, 2009). To do so, student teachers must observe different kinds of second-language classrooms in terms of organization, practices, and norms. Observation would enable them to develop awareness of the kinds and levels of possible classroom interactions because it can expose them to different teaching styles and provide opportunities for reflective thinking (Richards, 1998). To develop trainees' reflective thinking abilities, they should not only observe lessons, but also evaluate and reflect on them as well as on their actual teaching through guided oral and written reflections. According to Kupara-Spencer (2011), written evaluations of lessons are carried out through writing about what student teachers have done and what they have learned from their teaching experiences with the purpose of examining their teaching experiences and diagnosing their strengths and weaknesses, with a view to improving future lessons. Post-lesson discussions involve thinking retrospectively on what has been done in the lesson (Nyumwe & Mtetwa, 2011). Retrospective reflective thinking allows student teachers to explore the effectiveness of their instructional strategies (Galvez-Martin, 2003).

METHODOLOGY

Participants The participants in this study were six third-year female Arab students, who majored in EFL, in a four-year program for teaching at a teacher education college in central Israel. They were in early twenties and in the third year of their studies. The EFL teacher education program covers three areas: language competence and performance, teacher education in general, and language pedagogy in particular. The participants practiced teaching at a junior high school in a nearby Arab town. In the first year of the program, students only observed classes for one semester. However, they do practice teaching once a week in the second and third years. In addition, they practiced teaching intensively for five consecutive days twice throughout the school year. During this year in which the study was conducted, each taught once a week, for five hours, and I accompanied them in my capacity as pedagogical advisor. They also attended a didactic seminar course at the college which was designed to familiarize them with current pedagogy as well as with methods of teaching ESL/EFL in junior high schools. To better develop their reflective skills, the student teachers were also required to reflect on the required reading materials, class discussions and activities in this pedagogy course indicating things they liked or disliked, ideas they found relevant or important and the opposite and providing reasons for their preferences. To preserve anonymity, the participants chose pseudonyms which will be used throughout this paper:

DATA COLLECTION

The six student teachers were required to teach a lesson every week, observe two lessons, fill in observation sheets of lessons delivered by their mentors or by other student teachers, and participate in team meetings with their fellow students, the pedagogical adviser and their school mentors. For practice teaching, the student teachers were required to fill in a lesson plan sheet, which required them to describe their steps, prepare an extra task to help them survive in cases of emergency, evaluate their own performance and reflect on it while mentioning what activities should be used or should not be used in future lessons and why. The aim for filling in the last section of the lesson plan sheets was to support them in developing their reflective thinking skills by evaluating their performance, indicating strengths as well as weaknesses, and looking for alternatives for future lessons. The student teachers were also expected to make observation notes when they observed each other or the teacher educator. They completed a form in which they were expected to fill in the name of the observed student teachers, time, grade level, the performance of the observed student teacher and his/her interaction with the pupils. They were required to add their reflections pinpointing the successful activities and the less successful ones and providing reasons for their evaluation. Pre-lesson discussions took place in the didactic seminar course at the college which exposed them to current pedagogy as well as to methods of teaching ESL/EFL in junior high schools. In this course, the participants were required to reflect on the reading materials, class discussions and activities mentioning advantages and disadvantages, things they liked or disliked and others that sound important or relevant and providing reasoning for their opinions. Post-lesson discussions for evaluation were held in the mandatory team meetings which were attended by the student teachers, their school mentors, and the pedagogical advisor and were convened to discuss the students' preparation and practice. The six student teachers were also required to submit three portfolios throughout the school year: one at the end of the first intensive practical work week, another at the end of the first academic semester, and the third at the end of the second intensive practical work week, which coincided with the end of the school year. Besides the lesson plans and observation notes, each participant was expected to include three reflections in the portfolios to indicate whether they had experienced any changes in their lesson preparation and classroom performance.

DATA ANALYSIS

Qualitative data were derived from the above-mentioned sources which were systematically organized, coded, and indexed. Data sources were grouped by theme. For example, repeated data about developing reflective thinking skills obtained from interviews, field notes, meetings, and reflective texts were grouped together for interpretive analysis. In addition, the field notes that included class observations and team meetings were chronologically and thematically analyzed for developing reflective thinking skills. Sub-categories were also created and included the following: (a) developing self- reflection (b) resisting reflecting on peers' performance. Since the number of the participants was very small, statistical analysis was not considered. However, the answers of the participants on the pre-post questionnaires were compared to examine any change in the student teachers' reflective abilities.

DEVELOPING REFLECTIVE SKILLS AMONG ARAB STUDENT TEACHERS

To develop trainees' reflective thinking abilities, they should not only observe lessons, but also evaluate and reflect on them as well as on their actual teaching through guided oral and written reflections. Therefore, the participants in this study were expected to evaluate the lessons of their peers indicating which activities they liked and which activities didn't work well providing possible reasons. However, they resisted the idea of evaluating each other's performance, especially at the beginning. They tended to avoid peer evaluation. Notes taken at team meetings indicated that the students showed solidarity with each other and tried not only to support each other, but also to constantly defend each other. All of them held similar opinions to those of Zuzu. Over time they began to comprehend the reasons the pedagogical advisor wanted them to evaluate each others' lessons. Such an evaluation was aimed at appreciating differences and learning from each other, as each has her own personality, style of teaching, ideas, and abilities.

DISCUSSION

Difficulty in Reflecting on Teaching Experiences The data from the participants' reflection texts, reflective sections in the lesson plan sheets, transcripts of the team meetings and individual conferences, and interviews showed that they faced difficulty in reflecting on their teaching and observation experiences. This difficulty could be attributed to their previous learning experiences in which are based on transmission of material, memorization, copying and rote learning. As it has been mentioned by (Author, 2011; Al-Haj, 1996; Al-Issa, 2005, Collins et al. 2004; Sonleitner & Khelifa, 2005), it seems that these previous learning experiences affected their patterns of thinking. So they found it difficult to negotiate meaning, make decisions and rationalize their choices. Despite the difficulty in developing their reflective skills, some of them started to develop a journey of self-learning and self-discovery as a result of the constant attempt to reflect on their performance. In this sense, the argument of Ma and Ren (2011) about the importance of reflecting for self-study or learning is relevant. The findings show that the participants started to learn more about themselves as learners and what they need to improve their learning process. In addition, they started to realize the need of making the desired shift from having teacher-centered classes to learner-centered ones by involving the pupils more in their classes and to consider them in their preparation. These results are consistent with the calls of Suliman & Tadors (2011) to Arab students to make the needed shift from being passive learners to active ones. The data also showed that the participants made some improvement in their reflective abilities by adding rationale to their comments on their lessons. By the end of the school year, they became more objective in evaluating their instructional activities and pupils' interactions. Four out of six student teachers started to report both positive and negative experiences, mentioning both strengths and weaknesses and seeking possible solutions or alternatives. These results match the claims of Ferraro (2000) and Strakov`a of the need of developing reflective skills among pre-service teachers in general and Strakov`a's (2009) regarding EFL student teachers in specific for evaluating their teaching experiences and thinking of other ways for improving them. It could be concluded that they were at an embryonic stage in their reflective learning process as they were always defensive in the post lesson discussions. As Galvez-Martin (2003) and Nyumwe and Mtetwa (2011) argued about the importance of post lesson discussions for promoting retrospective reflective thinking to explore the effectiveness of instructional strategies, these sessions were helpful to some extent. It seems that the student teachers needed to practice teaching more and to participate in more post lesson discussion sessions. The student teachers kept a rigid attitude toward reflecting on the performance of their classmates.

LIMITATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

This is a small-scale study, but the results suggest that further examination of form of a follow-up research to be conducted a year or two after the completion of the teacher education program would be useful to investigate the effect of this attempt of developing their reflective skills on the process of their professional development and autonomy. Integrating thinking reflective practice in teacher education programs in the Arab world and in Israel and conducting a comparative study to compare between Arab Muslim female student teachers in these different settings would be another interesting idea for a future research. In light of the findings of this research, I recommend the following to better help Arab EFL student teachers develop their reflective skills:

- 1) Teacher educators are expected to be aware of the previous learning experiences and cultural modes that affect student teachers' behavior and performance. Since similar findings were revealed in other Arab Muslim countries, there is a need for teacher education programs' designers to take into their consideration the specific needs of Arab Muslim student teachers. As Littlewoods (2011) suggests there is a need to clarify and simplify the reflective teaching practice for Arab student teachers. Therefore, adopting reflective practice successfully would require teacher educators to follow a structured three-year plan for developing the reflective thinking abilities of pre-service teachers. Written reflections should be the core of such a program. In addition, it should be prepared and implemented step by step. In the first stage, they will be required to report only on positive experiences. The negative experiences will be reported including possible reasoning in the second stage. At the third one, the student teachers will provide alternatives to the activities that didn't work well.
- 2) To deal gently with the student teachers who avoid reflecting on the performance of their peers, teacher educators are expected to think of indirect ways rather than challenging them directly. For example, providing a list of written questions would be a good strategy especially at the beginning of the teaching practice. The aim of providing such a list is to encourage them to report about the performance of their peers and to reflect on their positive as well as negative experiences. The list would include the following:
 - 1) Indicate one good activity in the observed lessons today.
 - 2) How was the interaction between the pupils and the teacher?
 - 3) Are you fully satisfied from the pupils' participation?At later stages, the student teachers will be required to provide reasoning for their answers. At the third stage, they will be expected to suggest alternatives to the less successful activities.
- 3) Since the student teachers tended to avoid expressing their evaluations and reflections in the post-lesson discussions, one-to-one feedback should be considered at the early stages until they feel confident enough to hear comments from the pedagogical advisor in front of others. Individual student teachers and their school mentors should meet after lesson to discuss the student's performance using a special form that includes closed and open-ended questions. Some closed questions should be related to preparation and others to actual teaching, and the open-ended questions should be used to comment and reflect on the performance. For example, the list of closed questions would include the following:
 - 1) Which of the activities you used is the most satisfying?
 - 2) Are you fully satisfied from the participation of the pupils?
 - 3) How many new words have you taught in your lesson today?At later stages, they will be required to add the reasoning for their answers.

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